

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. Foreign language teaching methods are correct, mixed and comparative methods. Translation method these are essentially two-pronged methods of grammar-translation and text-translation. From the point of view of the grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for a general educational purpose. Grammatical exercises are performed with the aim of instilling the logical thinking of the language learner. Systematic grammatical theory was the main place in the content of teaching a foreign language in this method.

Keywords: method, foreign language, text, translation, means of communication, grammatical form.

ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. методы обучения иностранным языкам — корректный, смешанный и сопоставительный. Метод перевода — это по сути двуединые методы грамматико-переводной и тексто-переводной. С точки зрения метода грамматико-переводной иностранный язык изучается в общеобразовательных целях. Грамматические упражнения выполняются с целью воспитания логического мышления изучающего язык. Основное место в содержании обучения иностранному языку в этом методе занимала систематическая грамматическая теория.

Ключевые слова: метод, иностранный язык, текст, перевод, средство общения, грамматическая форма.

Language learning is considered one of the most important areas in the personality society.

The language, which is a means of communication, can be practically acquired in a natural environment, that is, in the family, among the public or in an organized way, that is, in a lesson.

Knowledge of linguistic phenomena, on the other hand, is studied theoretically. Most of the students and students currently studying are usually three languages. These languages are referred to in educational theory by special names native language, second foreign language and foreign language. The native language is the first language that has a special service in the formation of thinking the concepts in which native language words are borrowed are embodied in the embodiment of foreign language words in sound and writing during the learning of a second or foreign language.

Foreign language teaching methods are known and popular by four names. These are translation, correct, mixed and comparative methods. Translation method. Basically they come in two forms, grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of the grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for a general educational purpose.

Grammatical exercises are performed with the aim of instilling the logical thinking of the language learner. Systematic grammatical theory was the main place in the content of teaching a foreign language in this method.

The main functions of the method are as follows:

1. Language Teaching is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, the lexicon was also chosen subject to it. Grammatical exercises were the main way of working.
3. The grammatical rule was memorized and it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. The grammatical form and the meaning of words are revealed by means of literal translation.
5. By literal translation and memorization, the language material is mastered.
6. Words are limited to out-of-context, one-on-one memorization.

The purpose of the text-translation method is also aimed at general education, but the focus is not on the cultivation of logical thinking, as in the grammar translation method, but on the mental development of the language learner as a whole. The functions of the text translation method are as follows:

1. A foreign language is taught on the basis of written speech.
2. The link and often the text from the original were taken.
3. In the study of the text, a lot of effort and time was spent on analysis.
4. Method of opening the meaning of the word and grammatical form-translation.
5. Language material has been studied through translation and memorization of the non-Translational method.

This divides the method into two groups: natural lattice methods. One of the main functions of the natural method, the study of a foreign language should be appropriate for the conditions of mastering the native language. The main goal of the method is to be able to learn to read and write by teaching to speak a foreign language and learning to speak on everyday life topics. The most important of the main functions of this method is to create a language environment. An example of this is the creative work of method figures. M.Berlis method.

M.Berlis is an accomplished Methodist scholar in the history of Foreign-Language Teaching Methodology who founded and compiled textbooks on foreign-language teaching courses in the United States in 1878. M. The main methodological considerations of the Berlis system can be read from the cover of his textbooks:

1. The perception of language material should be immanent, without translation. The fact that the word is directly connected with the thought, that there is no connection with the words of the native language, as well as the perception of grammatical concepts in the context, without the participation of consciousness, without analogy with the native language.
2. Strengthening language material by imitating a teacher.
3. The absence of native language participation in the study of a foreign language.
4. Opening the meaning of linguistic phenomena with the help of exhibitionism.
5. First of all, the oral presentation of the new material.
6. Teacher and student paired speech (conversation), which encourages students to speak activity, is the optimal way of working from others.

F.Guen method. A French Methodist from representatives of the natural method, Guen advocated learning a foreign language in practice as if it were a native language. He was the first

in the methodology to discover the classification of lexicon by Subject (Life at home, school Society, nature). In the study of a foreign language, he proposed the following rule of law:

1. A person learns a language based on his needs.
2. Teaching unit is not a word made, the sentence is selected.

Mixed methods: as the reform of teaching foreign languages continued, It became noticeable that inexperienced (natural and correct) methods in public schools did not give the expected result. From the previous applied instructions, it was born to take lessons as a hybrid. it is an important factor in mastering the secrets of any profession, gaining qualifications and skills.

Knowledge of the Chem language represents a higher level of qualification of a specialist who is active in any field of the national economy.

For this reason, even if graduates of Secondary Schools have not set the goal of entering a higher educational institution, their deep study of a foreign language and acquisition of free-speech skills are very necessary for future specialists who aim to operate in various fields of national economy.

Among the most effective approaches to teaching a foreign language, it is possible to indicate language teaching methodologies in ICT, distance learning. Computer technology has a very wide range of possibilities, especially in language learning using the Internet.

They are manifested in the following:

- 1) to actively use in practice the acquired knowledge and skills in oral relations in a foreign language and learn to use the language materials received not only in his speech, but also in understanding the speech of a interlocutor whom he met through the Internet;
- 2) formation of a flexible skill to transfer acquired speech knowledge to changing situations of the relationship;
- 3) to organize a conversation that is carried out in the form of informal communication, to create a strong, immediate motivation to learn to speak and a motivation to react close to reality;
- 4) overcoming psychological barriers, in particular, avoiding speaking a foreign language and making mistakes, removing the barrier and internal and external reluctance, as well as the feeling of shame;
- 5) high level of educational quality and immediate effectiveness; training as early as the second exercise, users begin to speak a foreign language that they are learning in a speech mold given in the main training text; text exposure suggestive tools (including memory input) are used, and training is taken into account as early as the first exercise;
- 6) present and assimilate a large number of colloquial, high and grammatical units; in one presentation, 150-200 new words, 30-50 colloquial samples and several typical colloquial phenomena are introduced and mastered.

REFERENCES

1. Ахмедова С. Р. Таълим ва тарбия жараёнлари узвийлигининг самарадорлиги //Science and Education. – 2021.
2. Ахмедова С. Р. и др. Masofaviy ta'lim va uning horijiy tillarni o'qitishdagi o'rni //Science and Education. – 2021.
3. Methods of Teaching English: Учебное пособие для педагогических институтов

- и факультетов иностранных языков. — Л.: Просвещение, 1975
4. Ахмедова С. Р. и др. Инновацион технологияларни таълим жараёнларига татбиқ этиш йўллари //Science and Education. – 2021.